

Laser Assisted Excision of Intra-oral Capillary Hemangioma: A Case Report

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Abstract

Hemangiomas are benign vascular neoplasms originating from blood vessels. They present as elevated or flat reddish blue lesions and are usually solitary, predominantly affecting younger women. The growth may progress slowly, involving both superficial and deep vascular structures, and may impair function depending on its location. While most commonly seen in the head and neck region, oral involvement is rare. This case report aims to assess the efficacy of laser therapy in managing capillary hemangioma. The Nd: YAG laser offers superior hemostasis, precise tissue removal, minimal postoperative pain, faster healing, and improved patient compliance, making it a favourable alternative to conventional surgical techniques.

Introduction

Hemangiomas are developmental vascular anomalies and are considered by many authors to be benign lesions originating from endothelial cells.^[1] They are broadly categorised according to the type of blood vessels involved into capillary and cavernous variants. Capillary hemangioma is the most prevalent form, typically presenting as a small, localised lesion with relatively non-aggressive clinical behaviour. In contrast, cavernous hemangioma represents a more aggressive variant, often producing infiltrative lesions. The pathogenesis of hemangiomas is largely attributed to genetic and cellular mechanisms.^[2] Dysregulation of angiogenesis, leading to uncontrolled proliferation of vascular components, along with elevated levels of factors such as vascular endothelial growth factor, basic fibroblast growth factor, and indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase during the proliferative phase, is believed to play a key role.^[3]

Hemangiomas account for about 60%–70% lesions in the head and neck region. Clinically, these lesions appear as soft, smooth, or lobulated growths that may be either sessile or pedunculated, with dimensions ranging from a few millimetres to several centimetres.^[4]

The colour commonly ranges from pink to reddish-purple and may arise spontaneously or following minor trauma. Although most lesions are self-resolving, some may become symptomatic and necessitate treatment. Therapeutic modalities include surgical

removal, cryotherapy, embolisation, laser-based therapy, and corticosteroid use.^[5]

Oral hemangiomas are most frequently encountered on the gingiva and less commonly at other sites, including the palate, buccal mucosa, alveolar ridge, and salivary glands.^[6] Lesions involving the labial mucosa can lead to multiple complications due to their proneness to trauma, resulting in cosmetic disfigurement, repeated hemorrhagic episodes, and functional impairments affecting speech and mastication. This article presents the case of a 24-year-old female patient with a painless swelling of the labial mucosa, which was confirmed histopathologically as a capillary hemangioma and managed appropriately.

Case Report

A male patient aged 24 years reported to the Department of Periodontology, Santosh Dental College, Ghaziabad, UP, with a painless enlargement on the left labial mucosa in relation to the central–lateral incisors region in the last 7 months. A comprehensive intraoral examination revealed soft tissue overgrowth [Figure 1], which was pink in colour, soft in consistency, nonpulsatile on palpation, and sessile in origin, arising from the labial mucosa in relation to 41–42 region.

The margin of the lesion is about 6.5 mm × 5.5 mm in diameter with no secondary

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Discussion

Haemangiomas are considered hamartomatous lesions rather than true tumours.^[7] They most commonly occur in the head and neck region, with infrequent involvement of the oral cavity.^[8] Oral haemangiomas may manifest as small or large surface enlargements with varying levels of soft-tissue invasion, or as extensive lesions extending into the oesophagus. They may also present as multicentric lesions with a cobblestone-like appearance.^[8] The majority of small, superficial lesions, particularly those that are pedunculated, are capillary haemangiomas, whereas larger superficial or deeply located lesions are generally cavernous or of mixed histological types.^[9] Due to their rarity, these lesions can clinically, radiographically, and occasionally histopathologically resemble other conditions, resulting in diagnostic uncertainty.

Vascular lesions can be divided into those characterised by endothelial proliferation (hemangiomas) and those with normal endothelial turnover (vascular malformations). Although hemangioma is considered one of the most common soft tissue tumours of the head and neck, it is relatively rare in the oral cavity and is uncommonly encountered by clinicians.^[10] On the basis of the history given by the patient and the clinical examination, a provisional diagnosis of fibroma was made. A multitude of other lesions in the oral cavity can be resembled as hemangiomas, with the differential diagnoses comprising pyogenic granuloma (PG), chronic inflammatory gingival hyperplasia, epulis granulomatosa, telangiectasia, angiosarcoma, squamous cell carcinoma, and other vascular appearing lesions of the face or oral cavity, such as Sturge Weber syndrome.^[11] Therefore, microscopic evaluation is mandatory to come to a definitive diagnosis.

Pyogenic granuloma (PG) and hemangiomas can pose a diagnostic challenge for clinicians due to overlapping clinical features and a higher prevalence in females. Histologically, PG is categorized into two types: lobular capillary hemangioma (LCH) and non-LCH. The LCH variant is characterized by a thin endothelial lining surrounded by uniform proliferation of plump to spindle-shaped cells, whereas capillary hemangioma exhibits more prominent endothelial cells and a network of capillary-sized vessels arranged in a lobular pattern. In LCH-type PG, the capillaries are often oriented perpendicular to the surface. In contrast, fibromas demonstrate dense connective tissue with fewer budding capillaries compared to capillary hemangiomas. Considering the histopathological features along with clinical evaluation, a definitive diagnosis of capillary hemangioma was established.^[12]

Surgical removal of hemangiomas requires caution due to the risks of excessive bleeding and possible recurrence. Modern treatment options include steroids, electro-surgery, laser therapy, cryosurgery, and sclerotherapy, the latter being favoured for preserving adjacent tissues.^[13]

In this case, a soft-tissue Nd: YAG laser (1064 nm) was used based on clinical assessment. Nd: YAG lasers are popular in dentistry for their compact size, affordability, fibre-optic delivery, and ease of use. Nd: YAG lasers have been shown to reduce intraoperative bleeding, shorten procedure time, and ensure rapid postoperative hemostasis, with minimal complications such as scarring or discomfort.

Conclusion

Hemangiomas are common benign vascular proliferations; however, their infrequent occurrence makes it essential for dental practitioners to perform thorough clinical assessment and necessary investigations. Clinicians must be knowledgeable about the clinical presentation and management strategies for hemangiomas, taking precautions before surgical intervention due to the risk of sudden and excessive bleeding. Capillary hemangiomas frequently resemble pyogenic granulomas, requiring accurate diagnosis and appropriate treatment. Conventional surgical excision may result in significant haemorrhage, making laser excision a safer alternative.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest

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